

Welcome to SoLDAC Third Newsletter!

SoLDAC designs a system to convert CO₂ into ethylene

(1) COMET, (2) LOMARTOV, (3) IREC-CERCA, (4) CNR, (5) UDL, (6) EIM, (7) UEDIN, (8) USTAN

The Horizon Europe project SoLDAC entered the second part of its development and the Full Solar Spectrum, the Direct Air Capture and the Photo-electrochemical Conversion units' prototypes are being manufactured and optimised. This means that in a few months, the consortium will be able to work on the integration of the full SoLDAC system and start the demonstration phase, which is highly challenging.

The SoLDAC system will convert CO₂ into ethylene and C2 products through a 100% renewable, energetically self-sufficient and modular carbon-neutral solution, reinventing the ethylene industry and replacing the current carbon-positive routes.

Check out the website: www.soldac-project.eu

- Full name: Full Spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture and Conversion
- Acronym: SoLDAC
- Number of partners: 8
- Start date: 1 September 2022
- Duration: 36 months
- Total budget: 3 M €
- EC funding: 2 M €
- UKRI funding: 1 M €
- Partners acronyms: [COMET](#), [LOMARTOV](#), [IREC-CERCA](#), [CNR](#), [UDL](#), [EIM](#), [UEDIN](#), [USTAN](#)

PROJECTS NEWS

Developing and Shaping Nanoporous Materials for DAC

The search for adsorbents that can selectively remove CO₂ from air encompasses a wide range of materials with different surface chemistry. In SoLDAC we are developing nanoporous solids for this, where the very high internal surfaces can be exploited, and the interactions readily tailored.

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3rd General Assembly of SoLDAC in Messina, Sicily

On 29 February and 1 March, the 3rd SoLDAC General Assembly took place in Messina. We had the opportunity to continue working together and discussing the best way to bring SoLDAC closer to society.

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Power-to-X technologies: an energy storage alternative beyond batteries

P2X technologies rely on conversion of power (electricity) into gas or liquid fuels that can be further reconverted to power. This allows for decoupling the energy generation/use and supplying power to sectors that cannot be easily electrified (or rely on batteries).

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SoLDAC project connected with the main actors in public perception assessment of carbon capture technologies

On November 14th 2023, the SoLDAC project participated in the 'Public Perception and Business Models' workshop in Brussels. This workshop presented SoLDAC's social acceptance methodology.

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Participation of the University of Edinburgh in Electrochem 2023

Every year, the Royal Society of Chemistry organises the Electrochem Conference as a platform for early researchers to share their work. This year, the University of Bristol hosted the event, from September 10th to 12th and The Edinburgh Electrochemical Engineering Group (e3 group), led by Dr Ignacio Tudela-Montes, presented their work.

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Join the SoLDAC Stakeholders Community!

[I want to join!](#)

PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

Fabrication of Gas-Diffusion Electrodes for CO₂ Conversion: Effect of Sputtering Parameters

Article at the 10th Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. Partner(s): IREC-CERCA

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SoLDAC: Full Spectrum Solar-Powered Direct CO₂ Capture from Air and Conversion in Ethylene

Article at the 10th Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. Partner(s): SoLDAC consortium

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Screening and experimental evaluation of materials for water harvesting within Direct Air Capture thermally-driven cycles

Article at the 10th Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. Partner(s): CNR

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Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of CO₂-Adsorbing Metal Organic Framework "CALF-20"

Article at the 10th Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. Partner(s): LOMARTOV

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Assessment of coated monoliths for Direct Air Capture

Article at the 10th Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. Partner(s): UEDIN

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Electrodeposition of Cu-based bimetallic catalyst over Gas Diffusion Layer (GDL) for the electrochemical conversion of CO₂

Abstract at the Royal Society of Chemistry Conference 2023. Partner(s): UEDIN and IREC

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Optimised Electrodeposition technique for in-situ fabrication of Cu based catalysts on Gas Diffusion Layers for electrochemical CO₂ reduction

Abstract at the Royal Society of Chemistry Conference 2023. Partner(s): UEDIN and IREC

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MEET OUR PARTNERS

If you are new to our project, this is the place to start! Watch these short interviews and learn in their own words who they are and their role within SoLDAC!

LOMARTOV Interview

Edgar Contreras and Mihaela Mirea, from LOMARTOV, explain us in this interview their role within SoLDAC project and their tasks in WP6: Triple pillar sustainability guidance and validation.

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UPCOMING EVENTS

CAUC Technologies Workshop (Valencia, 30th May)

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Harnessing Renewables for a Sustainable Future: Exploring CCU, Power-to-X and Solar-to-X Innovations (EnergyVille, Genk, Belgium, 4th-5th June)

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SEED, International Conference on Sustainable (Valencia, Spain, 3rd-5th July)

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9th International Conference on Metal-organic Frameworks and Open Framework Compounds (EnergyVille, Genk, Belgium, 4th-5th June)

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<https://soldac-project.eu/>

Coordinator :

Partners :

Associated partners :

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Innovate UK

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